

between varieties, with two replications. A single row of check variety TN1 was included after every 10 test lines.

Planting of 3 1/2-wk-old seedlings was timed for the vegetative and flowering phases to coincide with major insect pest incidences. Fertilizer was applied according to local recom-

mendations, except more N was topdressed to attract higher brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* infestations. Damage was assessed during peak incidence of pests.

LF damage was assessed by counting total leaves and damaged leaves on 10 hills/variety; and BPH population/hill

was counted.

KD14-1-39, RP2068-18-3-5 (SwaradhanVelluthacheera), RP1579-58 and RP1579-1633 (Phalguna/ARC6650), and TNAULFR831311 (Co 41/Vaizaipoosamba) showed multiple resistance to BPH and LF in both the wet seasons (see table). □

Resistance of brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant rice cultivars to yellow stem borer (YSB) and gall midge (GM)

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We evaluated four rice varieties and eight prerelease cultivars with resistance to BPH against GM *Orseolia oryae* and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* during 1987 and 1988 wet seasons (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov), when there was severe insect pressure in the field. IR50 and TKM6 were the susceptible and resistant checks for YSB, Jaya and Mahaveera the susceptible and resistant checks for GM.

Ten plants from nonreplicated plots of each cultivar were selected randomly. Deadhearts (DH) were counted at maximum tillering and whiteheads (WH) at maturity. Silvershoots were

Reaction of rice cultivars to YSB and GM incidence in Kerala, India.^a

IET no.	Variety	Parentage	YSB		GM silvershoots (%)
			Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (%)	
	MO 4 (Bhadra)	IR8/Ptb20	27.4	12.1	15
	MO 5 (Asha)	IR11/Kochuvithu	15.6	8.3	4
8132	MO 6 (Pavizham)	IR8/Karivennel	22.2	18.3	3.5
8133	MO 7 (Karthika)	Triveni/IR1539	21.8	12.1	9.3
9287	KAU93	Jaya/Ptb 33	28.6	16.7	4.5
9266	KAU126	Jaya/Ptb 33	36.8	15.4	4.7
9288	KAU129	Jaya/Ptb 33	19.9	9.6	3.8
9267	KAU168	ARC6650/Jaya	26.7	15.4	4.2
9268	KAU170	ARC6650/Jaya	21.8	11.3	3.9
9381	KAU200	IR1561/Ptb 33	22.5	14.2	10.2
9384	KAU204	IR1561/Ptb 33	27.4	12.5	11.6
9380	KAU153-1	IR1561/Ptb 33	25.6	15.4	11.3
	IR50		100	100	18.0
	TKM6		21.4	18.8	9.2
	Mahaveera		25.2	15	0.4
	Jaya		49.2	30.5	52

^a Pooled mean data for 1987 and 1988 wet seasons.

counted 30 d after transplanting and related to tillers/plant for percentage incidence. DH were related to total tillers/plant and WH to productive tillers/plant.

MO 5 (Asha) and KAU129 were found to be resistant to YSB; others showed moderate resistance (see table). Seven cultivars showed moderate resistance to GM. □

Stress tolerance – excess water

Plant elongation potential of some advanced deepwater rice lines

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When excess water stays in the field for more than 1 mo, rice plant survival depends on a variety's ability to elongate above the water level. Total elongation during submergence

involves three components: leaf blade, leaf sheath, and internode.

We evaluated 14 entries, including checks Jalmagna and IR36, for elongation ability. Five seeds of each entry were soaked in 50-ml beakers for 24 h, then incubated at room temperature for 24 h. Uniformly sprouted seeds were sown in pots and plants raised for 40 d. Seedlings were submerged 1 m deep for 6 d.

The main culm of each plant was used to measure plant height and leaf

sheath, leaf blade, and internode elongation before and after submergence. Increases in plant height, leaf blade, and leaf sheath are given in the figure.

Plant height in IR48310-5-3, IR54300-50, IR48279-71-3, and IR33284-4-502-1-3-2-2 increased more than 50 mm/d (see table). Leaf blades in IR54300-50 and IR48310-5-3 increased 44 mm/d. Maximum leaf sheath elongation (20 mm/d) was observed in Jalmagna and IR33284-4-

Elongation potential of different plant parts in some advanced deepwater rice lines. Ghagharaghat, Bahraich, India. Values over the columns are increase in percentage.

Increase in plant height, leaf sheath, and leaf blade in some advanced IRRI deepwater lines and checks.

Variety or line	Elongation (mm/d)			Survival score ^a
	Plant height	Leaf blade	Leaf sheath	
IR31142-14-1-1-3-1-1-2	24	14	4	9
IR33284-4-502-1-3-2-2	52	21	20	5
IR33284-4-503-1-1-2-3-3	20	10	18	7
IR39509-46-3-2-2	23	21	19	9
IR39657-B-B-B-1	23	32	4	9
IR48279-42-2	23	16	16	9
IR48279-71-3	63	5	10	9
IR48279-73-2	25	22	7	9
IR48279-75-2	37	25	15	7
IR48310-5-3	63	44	10	3
IR5135-3-4	50	32	5	7
IR54300-50	62	44	19	5
Jalmagna	43	27	20	5
IR36	34	3	7	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

502-1-3-2-2. Internode elongation was not pronounced except in Jalmagna, IR33284-4-502-1-3-2-2, and IR33284-503-1-1-2-3-3.

IR48310-5-3 and IR54300-50 had the highest plant elongation potential, with survival scores of 3 and 5, respectively. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific understanding.

Stress tolerance – adverse temperature

Effect of low temperature on winter rice in Andhra Pradesh

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Sudden rice leaf yellowing and turning to orange were noticed in popular cultivars Tella Hamsa, Satya, Rasi, IR36, and WGL 48684 the last week of Feb 1989 in Telangana region, AP. Extensive surveys established that this had occurred within 2 d.

We examined the temperature data. On 19 and 20 Feb, the maximum temperature at Hyderabad was 34.4 °C. On 19 Feb, the minimum temperature was 16 °C. But on 20 Feb, minimum temperature was 7 °C. The sudden drop in temperature lasted 2 d. The rice cultivars were in different growth phases and were affected differently.

- IR36 had severe cold injury.
- Tella Hamsa and Rasi were in the vegetative phase, and had little cold injury.
- Tella Hamsa, in panicle initiation and boot leaf stages, had normal leaves. But 2 wk later, panicles were found to be chaffy. Pollen grains examined under the microscope were sterile.
- Low temperatures of 7-12 °C lasted 10 d. Severity of cold injury was proportionate to the variation in temperature.
- Plants in the shade exhibited the least cold injury symptoms.
- All cultivars affected by cold in the vegetative phase recovered when temperatures rose to more than 16 °C. The recovery of WGL 48684 was fast. Cold injury due to low temperatures observed in thousands of hectares necessitates a program for breeding cold-tolerant cultivars for the Telangana region. □